

REPORT PELAGIA CRUISE 64PE412

TREASURE

(Towards Responsible ExtrAction of SUBmarine RESources)

Horta - Horta 25 June – 13 July 2016

Gerard Duineveld and shipboard scientific party

1. INTRODUCTION

TREASURE (**T**owards **R**esponsible **E**xtr**A**ction of **S**ubmarine **R**esources) is a Dutch project funded by the Technology Foundation (STW) and industry with the aim to develop and test methodologies enabling the industry to properly monitor the impacts of deep-sea mining of SMS (Seafloor Massive Sulphide) deposits. SMS deposits contain a high percentage of metals like copper, zinc, gold as well as trace metals for industrial applications (e.g. electronics) (Hein et al. 2013), and are typically found near vent sites in seafloor spreading areas such as the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR). The protected Rainbow Vent site ($36^{\circ} 13.8' N$ $33^{\circ} 54.12' W$) is an example of a vent on MAR outside the EEZ containing SMS deposits (Marques et al. 2006; Hannington et al. 2011). The TREASURE project has selected Rainbow Vent as study area (Fig. 1) to test methodologies and approaches acknowledging that the area is protected under the OSPAR convention and is not a potential mining site. Moreover, the focus of TREASURE is on the background environment and fauna of the vent site and not on the active vents themselves as latter will be not be targeted by mining. In comparison to the active vents and their fauna, little to nothing is known of the background.

The TREASURE project covers 3 cruises (2014-2016) during which video-footage has been recorded, oceanographic measurements have been made using bottom moored instruments, and water and small sediment samples have been collected. The sampling is conducted in cooperation with colleagues from the University of the Azores and various other European universities. The Dutch TREASURE project has strong links with the European MIDAS project (www.EU-Midas.net) through exchange of data and scientific crew.

Fig. 1. Position of TREASURE work area (yellow rectangle) in relation to Azores (yellow dot, Horta)

For the 3rd TREASURE cruise (64PE412), the following primary activities were scheduled:

- recovery of moored equipment (2x landers, 1 x mooring) which had been deployed in spring 2015,

- collection of water (CTD) and seabed samples (boxcorer) at varying distances from Rainbow Vent,
- video surveys of the seafloor to supplement earlier recordings ,
- deployment of 2 seafloor moorings with thermistors for the duration of the cruise.

Primary focus of the sampling program will be put on the background physical conditions and associated deep-water fauna at varying distances from the active Rainbow vent. As secondary target a seamount was chosen ca 10 nm N of Rainbow Vent with a contrasting rich fauna on its flanks and summit (see map in Fig 2). Video recordings of the seamount had already been made in 2014 and 2015 TREASURE cruises.

2. WORK AREA, PARTICIPANTS & INSTUMENTATION

2.1. Work area

The work area of the cruise is shown in Fig. 2 which is based on RV PELAGIA's multibeam data collected in 2014-2015.

Fig. 2. Work area TREASURE cruise 2016. The red rectangle marks the Rainbow protected area. Blue rectangles mark the seamounts to the north and south of Rainbow

An overview of samples taken during 2014-2015 cruises is shown in Fig. 3 with red dots indicating water samples and rectangles indicating sediment samples. Blue lines denote tracks where video

recordings have been made of the seafloor and yellow lines denote continuous hydrographic measurements in TOWYO mode.

Fig. 3. Overview of samples taken during TREASURE cruises 2014-15. Lines mark video transects, circles ctd casts and rectangles boxcore samples.

2.2. Participants

	Name	Professional	Affiliation
1	Gerard Duineveld	Marine biologist (PI)	NIOZ
2	Marc Lavaleye	Marine biologist	NIOZ
3	Magda Bergman	Marine biologist	NIOZ
4	Lise Klunder	PhD marine biology	NIOZ
5	Danielle de Jong	student marine biology	RU Groningen
6	Jennifer Rasal	student marine biology	Univ. Liverpool
7	Maria Pia Nardelli	Marine biologist	Univ. Angers (fr)
8	Aurélia Mouret	geochemistry	Univ. Angers (fr)
9	Ulrike Hanz	PhD marine biology	NIOZ
10	Sabine Haalboom	Geologist	Univ. Utrecht
11	Francesco Cassano	student physical oceanography	Univ. Utrecht
12	Maria Rakka	PhD marine biology	Univ. Azores
13	Leon Wuis	mechanical engineer	NIOZ
14	Martin Laan	electronical engineer	NIOZ

2.3. Instrumentation

Video camera - recordings of the seafloor were made with the so-called hopper camera (Fig. 4), i.e. a tethered camera system capable of transmitting on-line HD video via an optic fiber to the ship's lab and the winch operator. The HD camera is directed vertically at the seafloor to allow quantification of the seabed features (organisms, lebensspuren) with the help of two green lasers mounted 30 cm

apart. The HD video stream is inspected and annotated on the ship and stored on disk. Every 10 s a still photo is automatically stored on disk. Besides the downward looking HD camera, the hopper system holds a forward looking camera for overview and avoidance of obstacles. The height of the hopper camera above the seafloor is controlled by the operator of the winch, i.e. a Kley-France winch with a 10 km Kevlar cable. The speed of the ship during recording is held at 0.5 knot.

Fig. 4. Hopper camera (left) and image recording and inspection at the ship's lab (right)

Bottom landers – different types of bottom landers were recovered during the 2016 TREASURE cruise.

- i) BOBO lander (Benthic Boundary Observatory- Fig. 5a) has its buoyancy and sensors raised at 2.5 m above the seabed. Each of the 3 legs of BOBO holds a ballast weight. BOBO is equipped with a downward looking ADCP (RDI 1200 KHz), a Technicap PPS4/3 12-cup sediment trap, Seabird CT16, and a Wetlabs' combined fluorometer/OBS (FLNTU)
- ii) ALBEX1 lander is a 2m high triangular frame with a single central ballast weight (Fig 5b). ALBEX1 is equipped with a Nortek Aquadopp single bin current meter, a Technicap PPS4/3 12-cup sediment trap, a Wetlabs' combined fluorometer/OBS (FLNTU), and a custom made plankton pump (ALTRAP)
- iii) ALBEX4 lander is of similar size and shape as ALBEX1. ALBEX4 is equipped with a Nortek Aquadopp Profiling current meter directed upwards, a Technicap PPS4/3 12-cup sediment trap, a Wetlabs' combined fluorometer/OBS (FLNTU), and a fish bait observatory. Latter consists of a timelapse HD video camera, 2 InfraRed LED lights, and a programmable 24 cup bait dispenser

Each lander had dual acoustic releasers (Benthos) connected to the ballast, and a radio and ARGOS satellite beacon and flashlight.

Fig. 5. A. BOBO lander recovered from a mission. Ballast at the base of each leg has been dropped. B. ALBEX1 lander with ALTRAP plankton pump

Mooring M1 – during the 2016 cruise a 1395m long mooring was recovered which equipped with a 75 KHz RDI ADCP and a NORTEK Aquadopp single bin current meter for current measurements, a McLane profiler for measurements of T,S, and OBS (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6. Preparation of the M1 Mooring in 2015

Thermistor mooring – 2 moorings with NIOZ built high resolution thermistors (van Haren et al 2009) were deployed for the duration of the cruise to measure internal wave activity and turbulence. One mooring with 200 thermistors was deployed in the hydrothermal plume ~1.5 nm NE of Rainbow Vent, and another with 100 thermistors on the summit of a neighboring seamount 10 nm N of

Rainbow. Thermistors were placed 20 cm apart. Both moorings were equipped with Nortek Aquadopp current meters and the one in the plume with a downward looking 75 KHz ADCP (see Fig. 7)

Fig. 7. Thermistor moorings deployed during the TREASURE 2016 cruise

Large Volume Sampler – large water samples (1000 L) for larval analyses were collected with the NIOZ Large Volume Sampler (Fig. 8). The top and bottom lid are held open during descent by a stepper motor and closed at a chosen depth by electric command transferred via the Kevlar cable. The depth reading of the LVS is displayed on the ship.

Fig. 8. NIOZ' Large Volume Sampler (1000 L)

Fig. 9. Video guided NIOZ boxcorer

Boxcorer – sediment samples were collected with a 50 cm diameter NIOZ boxcorer equipped with top-valve to prevent flushing of the core surface during ascent. An on-line HD videocamera was mounted on the corer which allow precise sampling of soft sediment patches in the generally rugged and rocky habitat around Rainbow (Fig. 9).

3. CRUISE LOG

Table 1 (below) contains a synopsis of the sampling stations, time of sampling, geographic position, type of activity, and comments. An overview of the various samples (e.g. Nutrients, DNA, Total Suspended Matter, Bacteriae etc) taken from the CTD-rosette casts at the different stations is given in the Appendix-1. The specifics of the SPM samples are shown in Appendix-2. The different cores taken from boxcore samples are summarized in Appendix-3 and photo's of the surface of the boxcores in Appendix 4. The location of the stations listed in Table 1 are shown in Fig. 10.

As stated earlier, prior to the cruise 2 target locations had been identified: i) the wider area around Rainbow Vent with its impoverished deep-water fauna (see Fig. 3), ii) a seamount ca. 10 nm N of Rainbow with a rich coral and sponge fauna which had already been visited during 2014 and 2015 cruises. Due to a difference in opinion with Portuguese Maritime authorities concerning a permit required for sampling near Rainbow Vent, 3 days after start of the cruise RV Pelagia was forbidden to work or enter in a 10nm zone of the active vent. This conflict had serious repercussion for the cruise plan, also because there were two moorings in the closed zone, i.e. one thermistor string deployed at the beginning of the cruise (st 1 in Table 1) and the M1 mooring deployed in spring 2015.

Because of the ban from the work area, activities during the remaining part of the cruise were relocated to the seamount, which was outside the exclusion zone, and to the southern and northern edge of the exclusion zone, roughly in the upstream and downstream direction of Rainbow and its plume. Also a seamount SSE of Rainbow was explored by video camera. In the course of the cruise, RV Pelagia received permission to recover the moorings from the exclusion zone which was done on 10 July.

Table 1. List of sampling stations with their date, geographic location, activities and comments. For a full account of the activities contact the authors.

STATION	Date	Latitude	Longitude	depth	Device name	Action name	REMARKS
1	28-06-16 16:46	36.2476	-33.8768	2101	thermistor PLUME	Deployment	~1nm NE Rainbow Vent
2	28-06-16 19:01	36.4369	-33.8651	542	videohopper	Begin track	upslope NW flank seamount
2	28-06-16 20:20	36.4372	-33.8611	585	videohopper	End track	entangled in fishlines
3	29-06-16 09:05	36.2220	-33.8796	2200	ALBEX1 lander	Recovery	
4	29-06-16 10:44	36.2217	-33.8802	1912	Boxcore	Bottom	~1 nm SE Rainbow
5	29-06-16 14:22	36.2636	-33.8651	2246	CTD with samples	Bottom	~2 nm NE Rainbow
6	29-06-16 16:27	36.2634	-33.8651	2116	Large Volume Sampler	Begin	~2 nm NE Rainbow; FAILED
7	29-06-16 19:09	36.3987	-33.8998	977	videohopper	Begin track	upslope NW flank Seamount
7	29-06-16 20:31	36.3952	-33.8962	778	videohopper	End track	
8	30-06-16 08:31	36.3956	-33.8961	723	videohopper	Begin track	continuing track st7 upslope
8	30-06-16 10:42	36.3902	-33.8895	805	videohopper	End track	
9	30-06-16 11:53	36.3927	-33.8936	683	thermistor MOUNT	Deployment	~3nm SW top seamount
10	30-06-16 15:33	36.2309	-33.9499	3000	BOBO lander	Recovery	
11	30-06-16 17:12	36.2571	-33.8787	2267	CTD with samples	Bottom	~2 nm NE Rainbow
12	30-06-16 20:32	36.2833	-33.8500	2720	Boxcore	Bottom	~4 nm NE Rainbow; FAILED
13	01-07-16 08:57	36.2833	-33.8501	2679	Boxcore	Bottom	~4 nm NE Rainbow 2nd attempt; FAILED
14	01-07-16 10:27	36.2570	-33.8800	2238	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	1.3 nm downstream Rainbow
15	01-07-16 12:33	36.2365	-33.8937	2118	CTD with samples	Bottom	0.5 nm downstream Rainbow
16	01-07-16 14:54	36.2365	-33.8942	2127	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	~0.5 nm NE Rainbow
17	01-07-16 15:49	36.2375	-33.8950	2143	videohopper	Begin track	~1 nm NE Rainbow
17	01-07-16 18:40	36.2284	-33.9041	2191	videohopper	End track	
Portuguese maritime authority: no permission to work within 10 nm of Rainbow							Departure from work area
18	02-07-16 08:28	36.3960	-33.8910	700	videohopper	Begin track	along crest seamount

18	02-07-16 10:39	36.4054	-33.8808	457	videohopper	End track	
19	02-07-16 11:22	36.4058	-33.8799	474	CTD with samples	Bottom	1 nm NE Rainbow
20	02-07-16 11:39	36.3853	-33.8820	1229	CTD1	Bottom	transect across seamount
20	02-07-16 12:37	36.3868	-33.8829	1166	CTD2	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 13:32	36.3884	-33.8840	1101	CTD3	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 14:21	36.3900	-33.8851	1040	CTD4	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 15:05	36.3917	-33.8860	970	CTD5	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 15:47	36.3933	-33.8872	876	CTD6	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 16:26	36.3949	-33.8882	793	CTD7	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 17:02	36.3966	-33.8893	686	CTD8	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 17:33	36.3982	-33.8905	548	CTD9	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 18:04	36.3998	-33.8915	672	CTD10	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 18:40	36.4015	-33.8927	820	CTD11	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 19:20	36.4030	-33.8937	893	CTD12	Bottom	
20	02-07-16 20:04	36.4047	-33.8948	968	CTD13	Bottom	
20	03-07-16 08:50	36.4061	-33.8958	1021	CTD14	Bottom	
20	03-07-16 21:39	36.4077	-33.8968	1019	CTD15	Bottom	
21	03-07-16 08:18	36.3973	-33.8902	533	CTD with samples	Bottom	~0.3 nm NE thermistor MOUNT
22	03-07-16 10:17	36.4053	-33.8833	472	boxcore	Bottom	~0.9 nm NE thermistor MOUNT; FAILED
23	03-07-16 11:24	36.4053	-33.8834	482	boxcore	Bottom	~0.9 nm NE thermistor MOUNT; 2nd trial
24	03-07-16 13:35	36.3855	-33.8817	1129	CTD with samples	Bottom	~0.7 nm SE thermistor MOUNT
25	03-07-16 15:16	36.3993	-33.8891	498	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	~0.5 nm NE thermistor MOUNT
26	03-07-16 16:32	36.4057	-33.8826	456	Triangular Dredge	Start Heave	~1 nm NE thermistor MOUNT; successful
27	04-07-16 08:42	36.4053	-33.8809	483	videohopper	Begin track	along crest seamount
27	04-07-16 09:51	36.4175	-33.8717	402	videohopper	Start Heave	
28	04-07-16 10:53	36.3935	-33.8868	758	CTD with samples	Bottom	0.36 nm E thermistor MOUNT on CTD transect 20
29	04-07-16 13:53	36.3984	-33.8994	1000	Boxcore with video	Bottom	~0.5 nm NW thermistor MOUNT
30	04-07-16 15:26	36.4015	-33.8925	625	CTD with samples	Bottom	0.6 nm N thermistor MOUNT on CTD St 20
31	04-07-16 17:08	36.3854	-33.8818	1145	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	0.7 nm SE thermistor MOUNT; FAILED
32	04-07-16 18:08	36.3853	-33.8820	1129	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	0.7 nm SE thermistor MOUNT; FAILED
33	04-07-16 19:02	36.3853	-33.8819	1145	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	0.7nm SE thermistor MOUNT; FAILED
34	05-07-16 08:53	36.2634	-33.8648	2279	CTD with samples	Bottom	3 nm downstream RAINBOW
35	05-07-16 11:21	36.3903	-33.8906	777	CTD YOYO	Bottom	0.2 nm E thermistor MOUNT; 33 casts 300-900m
36	06-07-16 09:09	36.0681	-33.9824	2035	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	~10 nm SW Rainbow
37	06-07-16 10:37	36.0686	-33.9818	2044	CTD with samples	Bottom	~10 nm SW Rainbow
38	06-07-16 12:39	36.0684	-33.9816	2054	Boxcore with video	Bottom	~10 nm SW Rainbow
39	06-07-16 16:37	36.2907	-33.6968	2050	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	~10 nm SW Rainbow
40	06-07-16 18:07	36.2907	-33.6967	2131	CTD with samples	Bottom	10 nm NE Rainbow
41	06-07-16 19:51	36.2908	-33.6966	2105	Boxcore with video	Bottom	video good; FAILED
42	07-07-16 08:15	36.2911	-33.6973	2245	video hopper	Begin	10 nm ENE Rainbow;
42	07-07-16 10:08	36.3002	-33.6857	2205	video hopper	Start Heave	
43	07-07-16 11:58	36.2994	-33.6866	2124	Boxcore with video	Bottom	10 nm ENE Rainbow;
44	07-07-16 16:45	36.0696	-33.9842	2085	video hopper	Begin track	10 nm SW Rainbow
44	07-07-16 19:37	36.0621	-33.9950	2126	video hopper	End track	
45_1	08-07-16 08:48	36.0654	-33.9792	2168	CTD1	Bottom	transect ~10 nm SW Rainbow 1300-2500m; WNW dir
45_2	08-07-16 09:39	36.0676	-33.9841	2066	CTD2	Bottom	
45_3	08-07-16 10:34	36.0699	-33.9886	2214	CTD3	Bottom	
45_4	08-07-16 11:36	36.0728	-33.9931	2268	CTD4	Bottom	
45_5	08-07-16 12:45	36.0754	-33.9974	2373	CTD5	Bottom	
45_6	08-07-16 13:57	36.0779	-34.0021	3399	CTD6	Bottom	
46_1	08-07-16 16:18	36.0711	-34.0136	2419	CTD1	Bottom	transect ~10 nm SW Rainbow 1300-2500m; ESE dir
46_2	08-07-16 17:15	36.0686	-34.0091	2316	CTD2	Bottom	
46_3	08-07-16 18:11	36.0659	-34.0045	2344	CTD3	Bottom	
46_4	08-07-16 19:10	36.0635	-34.0001	2121	CTD4	Bottom	
46_5	08-07-16 19:58	36.0609	-33.9953	3437	CTD5	Bottom	
46_6	08-07-16 20:51	36.0584	-33.9908	2150	CTD6	Bottom	

47	09-07-16 08:08	36.0446	-33.7680	1251	videohopper	Begin track	13 nm SE Rainbow
47	09-07-16 09:59	36.0356	-33.7571	808	videohopper	End track	Start Heave
48	09-07-16 10:47	36.0357	-33.7574	801	CTD with samples	Bottom	14 nm SE Rainbow
49	09-07-16 13:25	36.0412	-33.7650	785	CTD with samples	Bottom	13 SE Rainbow
50	09-07-16 15:30	36.1979	-33.6650	2400	videohopper	Begin	12 nm ESE Rainbow
50	09-07-16 17:14	36.1931	-33.6672	2437	videohopper	End	
51	09-07-16 18:12	36.1977	-33.6650	2440	videoboxcore	Bottom	12 nm ESE Rainbow
52	10-07-16 08:56	36.2553	-33.8789	2500	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	2 nm NE Rainbow
53	10-07-16 09:55	36.2615	-33.8571	2867	mooring	Recovery	retrieval mooring M1
54	10-07-16 12:46	36.2370	-33.8945	2400	Large Volume Sampler	Start Heave	0.5 nm NE Rainbow
55	10-07-16 14:44	36.2371	-33.8945	2880	CTD with samples	Bottom	calibration CTD
56	10-07-16 17:24	36.2487	-33.8777	2740	Lander	Recovery	retrieval thermistor PLUME
57	10-07-16 19:48	36.3921	-33.8920	2700	Lander	Recovery	retrieval thermistor MOUNT

Fig. 10. Overview of the stations listed in Table 1. Insets A-E show detailed locations. Grid marks 1 minute intervals.

Fig. 10A Stations sampled in the vicinity of Rainbow vent. Purple lines mark video transects. Yellow rectangles mark positions of ctd, casts and sediment or water samples

Fig. 10B. Stations sampled around the northern seamount. Purple lines mark video transects. Yellow rectangles mark positions of ctd, casts and sediment or water samples

Fig. 10C. Stations sampled in an area south of Rainbow. Purple lines mark video transects. Yellow rectangles mark positions of ctd, casts and sediment or water samples

Fig. 10D. Stations sampled in an area east of Rainbow. Purple lines mark video transects. Yellow rectangles mark positions of ctd, casts and sediment or water samples

Fig. 10E. Stations sampled around the southern seamount. Purple lines mark video transects. Yellow rectangles mark positions of ctd, casts and sediment or water samples

In addition to the info above, one of the cruise participants Danielle de Jonge (RUG Groningen) has written a personal Blog which been copied below:

Searching for the TREASURE - NIOZ cruise to the Rainbow Hydrothermal vent site from June 25th to July 15th 2016 Daniëlle S. W. de Jonge

The plane taking us to Faial (Azores) gave a beautiful view on the Pico volcano on the one side, and on the Research Vessel Pelagia in the Horta harbour on the other side. The volcano of 2351 meters is evidence of the strong volcanic activity in this area. The spreading of tectonic plates allows magma to rise up, resulting in the formation of new ocean crust: the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. Occasionally new islands come into existence (and may disappear again); the islands of the Azores were created this way. Our group of 25 - existing out of crew, staff, scientists and students - will be living and working on the Pelagia for about three weeks to conduct research on the volcanic activity in the deep sea.

At locations where plates are spreading, water trickles down the earth's crust, gets heated by magma, and dissolves many minerals in the process. This heated water rises back up to the ocean floor where it meets cold ambient water. Due to the temperature difference the dissolved minerals precipitate, forming chimneys from which black smoke seems to appear. This 'smoke' is actually a plume of hot water (up to 400°C) that contains many small particles. The plume can be carried over large distances by bottom currents. These systems are called hydrothermal vents and they sustain a unique ecosystem that depends on energy from the emitted chemicals like sulphide.

The minerals that precipitate include precious metals like copper, zinc, gold and silver, which are used in many technologies. It is therefore interesting to research if it possible to sustainably mine these metals. The TREASURE (Towards Responsible ExtrAction of SUBmarine RESources) project of NIOZ is focussed on developing a toolkit for industry to predict and monitor the impacts of potential mining. The Rainbow hydrothermal vent field (~2300 meters deep) near the Azores is the strongest known smoker of the Atlantic and therefore a good research area. This cruise is the last one for the TREASURE project: we want to collect the last data to finalize our report.

We arrived on Faial on the 25th of June, but couldn't leave until the 27th because the pilots (people that help big ships navigate the harbour) didn't work on Sundays! After sailing a day and a half we finally arrived in the Rainbow area. We started with deploying two moorings (long lines with many sensors held vertically in the water column by a buoy), so they could collect as much data as possible before we would retrieve them at the end of the cruise. These moorings can, for example, register temperature and currents over time for a certain depth range. Analysis of this data after the moorings have been retrieved can give us information on oceanographic features, like internal waves. Francesco Cassano (University of Utrecht) is a Master student working on this. We also retrieved two landers (large frames standing on the ocean floor with different types of equipment: sensors, baited camera, sediment trap, etc.) that have been in the area for over a year.

We started exploration of the Rainbow area and a seamount north of Rainbow. To get an idea of what these locations look like, we used a CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, Density) and the Hopper video. The CTD goes up and down in the water column to give us profiles of the temperature, salinity, oxygen concentration, chlorophyll, and turbidity with depth. If we saw a large peak in turbidity (how many particles are in the water) we knew we had hit the hydrothermal plume! We also saw a small bump in salinity around 1000 meters depth; it is thought this is water that has come all the way from the Mediterranean. The CTD also holds a rosette with so-called Niskin bottles: they can be closed at different depths to collect 12L of water. This water is then tapped for chemical and biological analyses. Jennifer Rasal (Bachelor student, University of Liverpool), Sabine Haalboom (Master student, University of Utrecht) and Ulrike Hanz (PhD, NIOZ) spent many hours in the cooled container (a mere 4°C while it was about 25°C outside!) filtering these samples.

The Hopper video was lowered to the ocean floor to observe the landscape and of course the fauna. The Hopper filmed thick plumes while we lowered our camera in the Rainbow area; a good indication that we were at the right location. We did a transect right over the vent site in the hope to see the smoking chimneys. Unfortunately, this was not the case. We did, however, observe many species that live in the surrounding area: a shark, sea cucumbers, orange cup coral, Acanella coral and shrimp. The landscape of the seamount was very rugged: many steep walls, peaks and rubble slopes. This habitat hosted a large variety of life: fish, sharks, sea urchins, shrimp, corals and sponges. Sometimes the sponges were so large it was possible for a small child to lie in them! In comparison to Rainbow the corals weren't spread out over the area, but present in dense 'forests'. Corals as far as the eye can see. The videos were annotated by Marc Lavaleye (NIOZ taxonomist) and Danielle de Jonge (Biology Bsc) for analysis afterwards. As the seamount is rich in life, it is also used as a fishing ground. Sometimes fish lines and ropes get stuck and remain on the seafloor. Our Hopper camera got stuck in such a fish line. Luckily we could retrieve it, but it had three lines stuck around the cable, which was damaged a bit.

Water samples were also taken by the Large Volume Sampler (LVS): basically a 1000L bucket that was closed at a certain depth. We had some issues with the closing mechanism at first - the lids didn't close properly which resulted in contaminated samples -, but after some smart adjustments it worked great. Lise Klunder (PhD at NIOZ) filtered this water with a plankton net to collect larvae to gain insight in the distribution and migration of species. She also works on metabarcoding by using new genetic techniques to unravel if DNA analysis of environmental samples (eg. a bottle of water or sediment) can give us a proper overview of fauna that lives in the area. For example, if she captures a scale or some slime lost by a fish, she can compare its DNA to a databank to identify its presence without having to use cameras. The water samples are taken from the CTD bottles and the LVS, and the sediment samples from the boxcore. The boxcore samples are also essential for Pia Nardelli and Aurelia Mouret (University of Angers, France), who work on the ecology and distribution of benthic foraminifera and the pore water biogeochemistry respectively, for Sabine Haalboom who works on the geochemistry of the plume and its sedimentation, Ulrike Hanz who works on the ecology and distribution of North-Atlantic deep sea sponge reefs, and Maria Rakka (University of the Azores) that works on bioprospecting deep-sea bacterial DNA.

Basically, the boxcore is also a big bucket that is pushed into the sediment by weights. A big lid with a knife on one end slides through the sediment and closes of the bottom. It has a video to guide us choosing a location with soft sediment, but as that didn't work the first couple of times we had to sample blindly. The boxcore struck hard sediment a couple of times and didn't close on one occasion. This resulted in great disappointment for all scientists and students who had waited about 1-2 hours (depending on the depth) to see if they could take their precious sediment samples. Not all attempts were in vein though! After succesful boxcores the sediment was described, photographed, cores were taken, and finally the sediment was sieved to collect the small organisms living in the sediment.

We had been sampling the Rainbow area for a couple of days when bad news arrived. The captain received a message from the Portuguese navy: we did not have permission to work in the Rainbow area as it falls within their Extended Economic Exclusion Zone. This message raised eyebrows, as we did not need permission for the previous cruises; what had changed? We left the area as requested, and conducted research in the area 10 miles around Rainbow while Gerard Duineveld (Chief Scientist, NIOZ) asked NIOZ to contact the embassy and arrange permission from the authorities. We did more research on the seamount North of Rainbow, another seamount South of Rainbow (which had an unusually high density of fish), and a deep basin that lies under the path of the plume. With the Hopper video we observed a rich area suitable for dredging, so we decided to take a small sample of sponges and coral. It was really exciting to get some specimens of the fauna that we had observed on the video. Corals that appeared green under the lights of our camera, actually turned out to be orange!

Unfortunately we did not hear from the Portuguese authorities about the permission for sampling. However, we did get permission to collect our moorings at the end, we just had to email them a date. So, it was decided to collect the moorings on Sunday the 10th of July and an email about this was send. When retrieving the moorings

on this day, we received another message from the navy. Apparently they didn't receive our email and we were requested to leave the area immediately and return to the Horta harbour. So, our cruise ended a day earlier than expected. In total we went to 57 stations; Magda Bergman (NIOZ) kept track of all waypoint and the administration of our data.

Everything taken into account, it was a good cruise. We managed to do most of the work we planned, and also got to explore new areas which is always an exciting endeavour. We saw many beautiful deep-sea organisms, got to work with advanced deep-sea technology, and had a good time together. We know have a better understanding of deep-sea ecosystems and made many new friends. Thank you all, we look forward to many more successful cruises!

4. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In the following sections contain some preliminary results from the ctd-casts and bottom lander deployment obtained during the cruise.

4.1. CTD series

Following is a graphic overview of results from series of CTD profiles made during the cruise. The first plot (Fig. 10) shows a CTD transect (st 20 in Table 1) (n= ?) across the seamount 10 nm north of Rainbow (see Fig. 10B). Note the bending of the isotherms near the slope.

Fig. 10. Temperature section across seamount 10 nm north of Rainbow.

On the 30 June a thermistor string was deployed (st 9) on the summit of the seamount in Fig 10. This MOUNT string covered the depth zone from 420-683 m water depth. On the 5 July (st 35) a series of repetitive vertical CTD profiles (YoYo) were recorded over the slope ca 400 m SE of the thermistor mooring. The depth zone covered by the YoYo was 300 to xxxx m water depth thus including the thermistor string depths.

Fig. 11. Time-series (n=33) of vertical profiles of water temperature close to MOUNT thermistor.

The time-series of vertical T-profiles (n=33) is depicted in Fig. 11 and suggests substantial short-term variation possibly due to strong turbulence.

In order to measure normal background turbidity without interference by the hydrothermal plume, two CTD transects were recorded 'upstream' of the vent site, i.e. 10 nm south of Rainbow (st 45, 46 - see Fig. 10C). Both transects ran parallel from the slope of the ridge into the deeper rift valley (Fig. 10C). Both transects show a consistent turbidity maximum (INL) around ~2000m water depth (Fig. 12). However, the absolute difference between concentrations in the upper water layer and the INL is small.

Fig. 12. profiles of turbidity (NTU units) along two parallel transects (st 45 upper panel, st 46 lower panel).

4.2. Lander measurements

One of the ALBEX landers (ALBEX-4) that was deployed in 2015 downstream of the Rainbow plume prematurely surfaced due to a leakage in one of the acoustic releasers. After a 14 d drift the lander was salvaged intact by an Azores fisherman. This particular lander was equipped with a dual time-lapse video system with IR illumination and a bait dispenser to attract deep-sea scavengers in order to monitor the species and their distribution over time. Fig. 13 shows the observations of fish in front of the camera over a year time i.e. April 2015-2016. During the winter period fish seems to be less abundant which is closely related to the abundance of amphipods (data not shown).

Fig. 13. Right: photo of a grenadier swimming over the bait dispenser on ALBEX-2 lander. Left: counts of fish seen on the video.

The other ALBEX lander (ALBEX-1) which was also deployed in spring 2015 upstream of the Rainbow plume, was successfully retrieved during the cruise. This lander carried an instrument package which included a Nortek Aquadopp current meter measuring the speed at 1 m above the bottom every 20 min. The record of current speed is shown in Fig. 14 incl. a 12h average. The record contains a strong semi-diurnal tidal signal and a spring-neap cycle (black line). Peaks in current speed coincide with increased acoustic backscatter suggesting local resuspension of particles.

Fig. 14. Record of bottom current speed 1 nm upstream of Rainbow ventsite. Black line is the 12h average.

Fig. 15. Crew and scientist of cruise 64PE412 in front of drawing painted on Horta ferry pier by the participants.

5. REFERENCES

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Rosette sampling list
RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-5-1
Date:	29-06-2016
UTC time:	13:30
Depth:	2318
EM302 depth:	2370

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2318	x	x							3.7	3.4	
2	2318	x	x							3.7	3.2	
3	2318		x				x			3.7	2.8	
4	2318		x	x						3.7	5.6	
5	2318		x		x					3.7	6.8	
6	2318		x		x					3.7	4.8	
7	2318					x				3.7	5.0	
8	2318					x				3.7	5.0	
9	2242		x	x						3.8	4.4	
10	2242					x				3.8	3.6	
11	1499		x				x			4.9	4.0	
12	1499		x	x						4.9	4.0	
13	1499					x				4.9	3.6	
14	1000		x	x						8.3	6.6	
15	1000					x				8.3	x	didn't close
16	2		x				x			22.1	18.4	
17	2					x				22.1	18.8	
18												
19												
20												
21												
22												
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-11-1
Date:	30-06-2016
UTC time:	16:30
Depth:	2344 m
EM302 depth:	2359 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2344	X	X							3.8	-1	
2	2344		X	X						3.8	1.2	
3	2344		X		X					3.8	2.4	
4	2344		X		X					3.8	0.8	
5	2344		X				X			3.8	0.8	
6	2344					X				3.8	3.4	
7	2201	X	X							3.8	-1.2	
8	2201		X	X						3.8	-1.2	
9	2201		X				X			3.8	-3.6	
10	2201					X				3.8	5.6	
11	1000	X	X							7.9	5.2	
12	1000		X	X						7.9	4.6	
13	1000		X				X			7.9	5.2	
14	1000					X				7.9	5.2	
15	1000					X				7.9	3.4	
16	5		X				X			22.1	18.2	
17	5					X				22.1	16.8	
18												
19												
20												
21												
22												
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-15-1
Date:	01/07/2016
UTC time:	11:50
Depth:	2216
EM302 depth:	2264

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2216	X	X							3.8	5.6	
2	2216		X	X						3.8	6.6	
3	2216		X		X					3.8	6.8	
4	2216		X		X					3.8	6.8	
5	2216					X				3.8	6.6	
6	2174	X	X							3.9	6.4	
7	2174		X	X						3.9	6.0	
8	2174					X				3.9	5.6	
9	1000	X	X							8.17	9.2	
10	1000		X	X						8.17	8.8	
11	1000					X				8.17	8.8	
12												
13												
14												
15												
16												
17												
18												
19												
20												
21												
22												
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-19-1
Date:	02/07/2016
UTC time:	11:10
Depth:	570 m
EM302 depth:	575 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	570	X	X							11.5	8.6	
2	570		X	X						11.5	7.6	
3	570		X		X					11.5	7.8	
4	570		X		X					11.5	7.4	
5	570		X				X			11.5	7.0	
6	570		X					X		11.5	6.8	
7	570		X					X		11.5	6.8	
8	570		X						X	11.5	6.6	
9	570					X				11.5	6.6	
10	570					X				11.5	6.6	
11	570					X				11.5	6.0	
12	251		X				X			14.8	9.8	
13	251					X				14.8	9.8	
14	74		X					X		17.9	14.0	
15	74		X					X		17.9	14.0	
16	74		X						X	17.9	9.2	
17	74					X				17.9	10.4	
18	5		X				X			22.4	16.2	
19	5		X					X		22.4	17.0	
20	5		X					X		22.4	17.6	
21	5		X						X	22.4	17.8	
22	5					X				22.4	18.0	
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-21-1
Date:	03/07/2016
UTC time:	08:05
Depth:	627 m
EM302 depth:	641 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUIS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	627	X	X							10.69	7.2	
2	627		X	X						10.69	6.4	
3	627		X		X					10.69	6.4	
4	627		X		X					10.69	5.8	
5	627		X				X			10.69	5.8	
6	627		X					X		10.69	5.0	
7	627		X					X		10.69	4.6	
8	627		X						X	10.69	4.4	
9	627					X				10.69	4.6	
10	627					X				10.69	4.0	
11	627					X				10.69	4.4	
12	299		X				X			14.9	9.6	
13	299									14.9	9.4	
14	100		X					X		17.9	13.2	
15	100		X					X		17.9	13.6	
16	100		X						X	17.9	13.6	
17	100					X				17.9	13.6	
18	4		X				X			22.2	18.8	
19	4		X					X		22.2	19.0	
20	4		X					X		22.2	19.4	
21	4		X						X	22.2	19.8	
22	4					X				22.2	19.8	
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-24-1
Date:	03/07/2016
UTC time:	13:10
Depth:	1231 m
EM302 depth:	1242 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	1231	X	X							6.5	1.6	
2	1231		X	X						6.5	0.6	
3	1231	X	X							6.5	0.6	
4	1231		X		X					6.5	0.4	
5	1231		X		X					6.5	0.0	
6	1231		X					X		6.5	-0.6	
7	1231		X					X		6.5	-0.6	
8	1231		X						X	6.5	-2.2	
9	1231					X				6.5	-2.0	
10	1231					X				6.5	-1.2	
11	1231					X				6.5	-1.6	
12	700		X					X		10.1	1.8	
13	700		X					X		10.1	1.6	
14	700		X						X	10.1	1.4	
15	700					X				10.1	0.8	
16	69		X					X		17.9	10.2	
17	69		X					X		17.9	10.0	
18	69		X						X	17.9	9.6	
19	69					X				17.9	9.8	
20	5		X					X		22.4	15.0	
21	5		X					X		22.4	15.0	
22	5		X						X	22.4	15.2	
23	5					X				22.4	15.2	
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-28-1
Date:	04/07/2016
UTC time:	10:35
Depth:	907 m
EM302 depth:	925 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	907	X	X							8.8	5.6	
2	907		X	X						8.8	4.4	
3	907		X		X					8.8	4.0	
4	907		X		X					8.8	4.2	
5	907		X					X		8.8	3.6	
6	907		X					X		8.8	3.2	
7	907		X						X	8.8	3.2	
8	907					X				8.8	3.0	
9	907					X				8.8	3.0	
10	75		X					X		18.0	14.4	
11	75		X					X		18.0	14.6	
12	75		X						X	18.0	14.6	
13	75					X				18.0	14.8	
14	5		X					X		22.3	19.8	
15	5		X					X		22.3	19.8	
16	5		X						X	22.3	19.8	
17	5					X				22.3	19.8	
18												
19												
20												
21												
22												
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-30-1
Date:	04/07/2016
UTC time:	15:10
Depth:	827 m
EM302 depth:	847 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	827	X	X							9.7	7.6	Were on a steep slope, altimeter went from 5 to 15 meter while closing bottles
2	827		X	X						9.7	5.6	
3	827		X		X					9.7	5.6	
4	827		X		X					9.7	5.4	
5	827		X				X			9.7	3.6	
6	827		X					X		9.7	3.2	
7	827		X					X		9.7	3.2	
8	827		X						X	9.7	3.4	
9	827					X				9.7	3.0	
10	827					X				9.7	2.8	
11	409						X			13.2	6.6	
12	409					X				13.2	6.8	
13	180							X		15.7	9.4	
14	180							X		15.7	9.6	
15	180					X				15.7	9.6	
16	60							X		18.7	13.8	
17	60							X		18.7	13.6	
18	60								X	18.7	13.6	
19	60					X				18.7	13.8	
20	5						X			22.3	18.2	
21	5							X		22.3	18.4	
22	5							X		22.3	18.6	
23	5								X	22.3	18.8	
24	5					X				22.3	19.2	

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-37-1
Date:	06/07/2016
UTC time:	10:00
Depth:	2162 m
EM302 depth:	2166 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2162	X	X							3.9	7.8	
2	2162		X	X						3.9	6.8	
3	2162		X		X					3.9	6.6	
4	2162		X		X					3.9	6.8	
5	2162		X				X			3.9	6.6	
6	2162		X					X		3.9	5.8	
7	2162		X					X		3.9	5.6	
8	2162		X						X	3.9	5.6	
9	2162					X				3.9	5.6	
10	2162					X				3.9	5.4	
11	1999	X	X							4.0	5.2	
12	1999			X		X				4.0	5.6	
13	1499	X	X							5.3	6.2	
14	1499		X	X						5.3	6.2	
15	1499		X				X			5.3	6.4	
16	1499					X				5.3	6.4	
17	999			X						8.2	8.2	
18	999					X				8.2	8.4	
19	85							X		17.7	16.4	
20	85							X		17.7	17.0	
21	85								X	17.7	16.4	
22	85					X				17.7	17.0	
23	5						X			22.6	20.8	
24	5					X				22.6	21.0	

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-40-1
Date:	06/07/2016
UTC time:	17:25
Depth:	2307 m
EM302 depth:	2311 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2307	X	X							3.8	7.8	
2	2307		X	X			X		X	3.8	6.8	
3	2307				X					3.8	6.8	
4	2307				X					3.8	6.4	
5	2307							X		3.8	6.4	
6	2307							X		3.8	6.4	
7	2307					X				3.8	6.4	
8	2307					X				3.8	5.6	
9	2150	X	X							3.9	6.0	
10	2150		X	X						3.9	5.6	
11	2150					X				3.9	5.4	
12	1500	X	X							5.5	5.8	
13	1500		X	X			X			5.5	5.6	
14	1500					X				5.5	5.6	
15	999		X	X						8.2	7.4	
16	999					X				8.2	7.8	
17	74							X		18.2	16.0	
18	74							X		18.2	16.4	
19	74								X	18.2	16.6	
20	74					X				18.2	16.6	
21	4						X		X	22.9	20.2	
22	4							X		22.9	20.2	
23	4							X		22.9	20.6	
24	4					X				22.9	22.8	

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-45-6
Date:	08/07/2016
UTC time:	13:35
Depth:	2390 m
EM302 depth:	2411 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2390	X	X							3.7	7.2	
2	2390		X	X			X		X	3.7	6.6	
3	2390		X		X					3.7	6.6	
4	2390		X		X					3.7	6.4	
5	2390		X					X		3.7	6.0	
6	2390		X					X		3.7	5.8	
7	2390					X				3.7	5.6	
8	2390					X				3.7	5.8	
9	1940	X	X							4.0	5.8	
10	1940		X	X						4.0	5.6	
11	1940					X				4.0	5.4	
12	1499	X	X							5.3	6.8	
13	1499		X	X						5.3	5.6	
14	1499					X				5.3	5.6	
15	1000		X	X						8.3	8.0	
16	1000					X				8.3	8.2	
17	90		X					X		17.8	15.8	
18	90		X					X		17.8	16.2	
19	90		X						X	17.8	16.6	
20	90					X				17.8	16.6	
21	3		X					X		23.0	21.4	
22	3		X					X		23.0	21.4	
23	3		X				X		X	23.0	21.6	
24	3					X				23.0	21.6	

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-48-01
Date:	09/07/2016
UTC time:	10:30
Depth:	840 m
EM302 depth:	840 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	840	X	X							9.1	11.8	
2	840		X	X						9.1	10.6	
3	840		X		X					9.1	10.2	
4	840		X		X					9.1	10.0	
5	840		X				X			9.1	9.6	
6	840		X					X		9.1	9.6	
7	840		X					X		9.1	9.6	
8	840		X						X	9.1	9.4	
9	840					X				9.1	9.4	
10	840					X				9.1	9.4	
11	840					X				9.1	9.4	
12	400		X				X			13.5	13.2	
13	400					X				13.5	13.2	
14	100		X					X		17.8	17.0	
15	100		X					X		17.8	17.0	
16	100		X						X	17.8	17.0	
17	100					X				17.8	17.0	
18	4		X				X			22.8	21.4	
19	4		X					X		22.8	21.6	
20	4		X					X		22.8	21.6	
21	4		X						X	22.8	21.6	
22	4					X				22.8	21.6	
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-49-01
Date:	09/07/2016
UTC time:	13:00
Depth:	1052 m
EM302 depth:	1042 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	1052	X	X							7.8	9.6	
2	1052		X	X						7.8	9.4	
3	1052		X		X					7.8	9.4	
4	1052		X		X					7.8	9.2	
5	1052		X		X					7.8	9.0	
6	1052		X		X					7.8	8.6	
7	1052		X		X					7.8	9.2	
8	1052		X		X					7.8	9.0	
9	1052		X					X		7.8	8.6	
10	1052		X					X		7.8	8.6	
11	1052		X						X	7.8	8.6	
12	1052					X				7.8	8.6	
13	1052					X				7.8	8.2	
14	1052					X				7.8	8.6	
15	74		X					X		17.8	17.6	
16	74		X					X		17.8	17.8	
17	74		X						X	17.8	17.8	
18	74					X				17.8	17.8	
19	4		X					X		22.9	22.0	
20	4		X					X		22.9	22.6	
21	4		X						X	22.9	22.6	
22	4					X				22.9	22.6	
23												
24												

Rosette sampling list

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE

Station/Cast:	64PE412-55-01
Date:	10/07/2016
UTC time:	13:45
Depth:	2287 m
EM302 depth:	2295 m

NiskinBottle	Depth (m)	NIOZ					UAç	Ulrike		Tinsitu (°C)	Tdeck (°C)	Remarks
		TSPM	NUTS	DNA bacteria	eDNA fish	Spare	DNA, POM	SPOM	DIC, DOC,			
1	2287					X				3.7	6.6	
2	2287					X				3.7	6.2	
3	2287					X				3.7	6.2	
4	2287					X				3.7	6.2	
5	2139	X								3.8	5.8	
6	2139	X								3.8	6.2	
7	2139	X								3.8	5.8	
8	2139					X				3.8	5.8	
9	1960	X								4.0	5.6	
10	1960	X								4.0	5.6	
11	1960	X								4.0	5.8	
12	1960					X				4.0	5.8	
13	1500	X								5.4	6.6	
14	1500	X								5.4	6.6	
15	1500	X								5.4	6.6	
16	1500					X				5.4	6.2	
17												
18												
19												
20												
21												
22												
23												
24												

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE SPM Filters

Station/Cast	Bottle	Depth	Portion	Filter	Remarks
ST05-01	1	2318	A	15.101	5 liter
ST05-01	1	2318	B	15.102	5 liter
ST05-01	2	2318	A	15.103	5 liter
ST05-01	2	2318	B	15.104	5 liter
ST11-01	1	2314	A	15.105	5 liter
ST11-01	1	2314	B	15.106	5 liter
ST11-01	7	2201	A	15.107	5 liter
ST11-01	7	2201	B	15.108	5 liter
ST11-01	11	1001	A	15.109	5 liter
ST11-01	11	1001	B	15.110	5 liter
ST15-01	1	2216	A	15.111	5 liter
ST15-01	1	2216	B	15.112	5 liter
ST15-01	6	2174	A	15.113	5 liter
ST15-01	6	2174	B	15.114	5 liter
ST15-01	9	1000	A	15.115	5 liter
ST15-01	9	1000	B	15.116	5 liter
ST19-01	1	570	A	15.117	5 liter
ST19-01	1	570	B	15.118	5 liter
Blank	-	-	-	15.119	-
Blank	-	-	-	15.120	-
ST21-01	1	627	A	15.121	5 liter
ST21-01	1	627	B	15.122	5 liter
ST24-01	1	1231	A	15.123	5 liter
ST24-01	1	1231	B	15.124	5 liter
ST24-01	3	1231	A	15.127	5 liter
ST24-01	3	1231	B	15.126	5 liter
ST28-01	1	907	A	15.128	5 liter
ST28-01	1	907	B	15.129	5 liter
ST30-01	1	827	A	15.130	5 liter
ST30-01	1	827	B	15.131	5 liter
ST37-01	1	2162	A	15.132	5 liter
ST37-01	1	2162	B	15.133	5 liter
ST37-01	11	1999	A	15.134	5 liter
ST37-01	11	1999	B	15.135	5 liter
ST37-01	13	1499	A	15.136	5 liter
ST37-01	13	1499	B	15.137	5 liter

Filter 15.125 got wrapped up while trying to place it on the filter cup.

RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE
SPM Filters; skipped filter 15.140

Station/Cast	Bottle	Depth	Portion	Filter	Remarks
Blank	-	-	-	15.138	-
Blank	-	-	-	15.139	-
ST40-01	1	2307	A	15.141	5 liter
ST40-01	1	2307	B	15.142	5 liter
ST40-01	9	2150	A	15.143	5 liter
ST40-01	9	2150	B	15.144	5 liter
ST40-01	12	1500	A	15.145	5 liter
ST40-01	12	1500	B	15.146	5 liter
ST45-06	1	2390	A	15.147	5 liter
ST45-06	1	2390	B	15.148	5 liter
ST45-06	9	1940	A	15.149	5 liter
ST45-06	9	1940	B	15.150	5 liter
ST45-06	12	1499	A	15.151	5 liter
ST45-06	12	1499	B	15.152	5 liter
ST48-01	1	840	A	15.153	Filter folded during filtration → not the complete 5L on the filter
ST48-01	1	840	B	15.154	5 liter
ST49-01	1	1052	A	15.155	5 liter
ST49-01	1	1052	B	15.156	5 liter
Blank	-	-	-	15.157	-
Blank	-	-	-	15.158	-
ST55-01	5	2139	A	15.159	5 liter
ST55-01	5	2139	B	15.160	5 liter
ST55-01	6	2139	A	15.161	5 liter
ST55-01	6	2139	B	15.162	5 liter
ST55-01	7	2139	A	15.163	5 liter
ST55-01	7	2139	B	15.164	5 liter
ST55-01	9	1960	A	15.165	Filter folded after filtration
ST55-01	9	1960	B	15.166	Filter dropped after filtration
ST55-01	10	1960	A	15.167	5 liter
ST55-01	10	1960	B	15.168	5 liter
ST55-01	11	1960	A	15.169	5 liter
ST55-01	11	1960	B	15.170	5 liter
ST55-01	13	1500	A	15.171	5 liter
ST55-01	13	1500	B	15.172	5 liter
ST55-01	14	1500	A	15.173	5 liter
ST55-01	14	1500	B	15.174	5 liter

**RV Pelagia cruise 64PE412 – TREASURE
SPM Filters**

Station/Cast	Bottle	Depth	Portion	Filter	Remarks
ST55-01	15	1500	A	15.175	5 liter
ST55-01	15	1500	B	15.176	5 liter
Blank	-	-	-	15.177	-
Blank	-	-	-	15.178	-

Appendix 3 – Boxcore samples

Type and number of subcores taken from the boxcore samples

Box	Sediment	Undisturbed bed	Video	Bio sample (>200um)	DNA sample (>200um)	DNA syringes	Geo core	O ₂ profile core	GeoChem core
4	y	y	-	y	y	3x	1x	1x	1x
12	empty	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	empty	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22	very little	n	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	y	y	-	y	y	3x	2x	2x	1x
29	y	y	y	y	y	3x	2x	2x	1x
38	y	y	y	y	y	3x	1x	2x	1x
41	empty	-	y	-	-	-	-	-	-
43	y	y	y	y	y	3x	2x	2x	1x
51	y	y	y	y	y	3x	2x	2x	1x

Appendix 4 – Boxcore photographs and descriptions

Description Boxcores

ST04 (29/06/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. At the highest point of the boxcore it was 37 cm in height, at the lowest point 27 cm. The sediment has a light brownish/yellowish colour, which became slightly more greyish in colour in the lower 10 to 15 cm of the boxcore. The sediment had a clayish (sticky and slurish) behaviour and was very fine grained. Within the boxcore several terapods, quivolina's, beaks from squids and polychaete tubes were found. Manganese cores(?) were also found.

ST22 (03/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. The water inside the boxcorer is milky, but unfortunately there is only a small layer of sediment; practically empty. No geocores were taken. The sediment was fine grained and very light coloured. Some scleractinia rubble, brachipod shells and small pinkish ophiuroids were present.

ST23 (03/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. At the highest point of the boxcore it was 21 cm in height, at the lowest point 12 cm. The sediment is very light coloured and fine grained. Some darker coarser grains are present in patches, and also some scleractinia rubble. On top is a medium sized brittle star.

ST29 (04/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. No significant difference in height of core surface: 30 cm. We were unable to tap all water from the top; there was still some left while taking

Appendix 4 –Boxcore photographs and descriptions

the cores. The sediment is very light brown coloured and fine grained. Some darker coarser grains are present in patches. A Hesionidae polychaete was present at the surface. Layering: 1) Top layer, ~3cm thick, fine grains, 2) Coarser darker layer below, ~ 2cm thick, 3) Large clay clay, very fine, little coarse sediment mixed, 4) Coarse layer ~5 cm, includes rock fragments and scleractinia rubble, 5) Finer bottom layer.

ST38 (06/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. At the highest point of the boxcore it was 42.5 cm in height, at the lowest point 37 cm. The top half of the sediment is very light brown coloured and fine grained clay. Very sticky and solid. The clay lies on a very 'watery' layer which easily washes away. The second half of the boxcore is coarser grained (sandy) also light brown coloured. On the surface is some Lophelia rubble, polychaete burrows and pteropod shells.

ST43 (07/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. At the highest point of the boxcore it was 50 cm in height, at the lowest point 44 cm. The top half of the sediment is very light brown coloured and fine grained clay. Very sticky and solid. The clay lies on a very 'watery' layer which easily washes away. This boundary is not horizontal but tilted. The second half of the boxcore is coarser grained (sandy) also light brown coloured. On the surface is no rubble or gravel, just a few pteropod shells and 2 polychaete tubes.

ST51 (09/07/2016)-The boxcore had a diameter of 50 cm. At the highest point of the boxcore it was 26 cm in height, at the lowest point 20 cm. The sediment is clay: very fine grained, light-brown, quite sticky and rigid. The surface of the boxcore is cracked. On top of the sediment lie some pteropod shells and a small stone, and a polychaete burrow is present. There is no layering in the core. There are however greyish spots inside the sediment at different depths, probably weathering of some sort (see picture). Also, a piece of stony coral and some darker clay patches were found inside the clay.